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Spontaneous functional recovery after focal damage in neuronal cultures

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MANUSCRIPT TITLE PAGE

Manuscript Title (50 word maximum):

Spontaneous functional recovery after focal damage in neuronal cultures

Abbreviated Title (50 character maximum) Recovery in Neuronal Cultures after Damage**Authors:**

Sara Teller^{1,2}, Estefanía Estévez-Priego^{1,2}, Clara Granell^{2,3,4}, Daniel Tornero^{5,6}, Jordi Andilla⁷, Omar E. Olarte⁷, Pablo Loza-Alvarez⁷, Alex Arenas⁸, and Jordi Soriano^{1,2}

¹Departament de Física de la Matèria Condensada, Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.

²Universitat de Barcelona Institute of Complex Systems (UBICS), Barcelona, Spain.

³ GOTHAM Lab – Institute for Biocomputation and Physics of Complex Systems (BIFI), University of Zaragoza, Spain.

⁴ Department of Condensed Matter Physics, University of Zaragoza, Spain

⁵Departament de Biomedicina, Facultat de Medicina, Institut de Neurociències, Universitat de Barcelona, Spain.

⁶Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red sobre Enfermedades Neurodegenerativas (CIBERNED).

⁷ICFO - Institut de Ciències Fotòniques, The Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology, Castelldefels, Spain.

⁸Departament d'Enginyeria Informàtica i Matemàtiques, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Tarragona, Spain.

Author Contributions:

JS, ST, JA and PL designed research. ST, OO and JA performed research. ST, EE, CC, and AA contributed unpublished reagents/analytic tools. ST, EE, DT and JS analyzed data. ST, DT and JS wrote the paper.

Correspondence should be addressed to

Jordi Soriano

Departament de Física de la Matèria Condensada, Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.

Phone: +34934020554

jordi.soriano@ub.edu

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Spontaneous functional recovery after focal damage in neuronal cultures

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1 **Abstract**

2 Damage in biological neuronal networks triggers a complex functional reorganization whose mechanisms
3 are still poorly understood. To delineate this reorganization process, here we investigate the functional
4 alterations of *in vitro* rat cortical circuits following localized laser ablation. The analysis of the functional
5 network configuration before and after ablation allowed us to quantify the extent of functional alterations
6 and the characteristic spatial and temporal scales along recovery. We observed that damage precipitated
7 a fast rerouting of information flow that restored network's communicability in about 15 min. Functional
8 restoration was led by the immediate neighbors around trauma but was orchestrated by the entire network.
9 Our *in vitro* setup exposes the ability of neuronal circuits to articulate fast responses to acute damage, and
10 may serve as a proxy to devise recovery strategies in actual brain circuits. Moreover, this biological setup
11 can become a benchmark to empirically test network theories about the spontaneous recovery in dynamical
12 networks.

13 **Significance Statement**

14 Given the sheer size of the brain, *in vitro* models in the form of neuronal cultures have emerged as a promis-
15 ing tool to investigate dynamic and network alterations in detail upon physical damage. Here we present a
16 new experimental paradigm based on the combination of laser microsurgery and calcium fluorescence imag-
17 ing to analyze network functional alterations after a focal lesion. We show that the network is not only able

18 to cope with damage but that the regions around the lesion core actively participate in recovery, restoring
19 the initial network activity levels in just 15 min. Our approach offers interesting perspectives for modeling
20 network functional loss and recovery in a number of damage actions, from stroke to degenerative disorders.

21 **Introduction**

22 The functional affectations in a neuronal circuit that arise from focal damage are complex. In the brain,
23 the traumatic loss of neuronal tissue irreversibly disables the lesioned site and silences the connectivity
24 pathways emerging from and converging upon it (Carrera and Tononi, 2014; Fornito et al., 2015). Damage
25 leads to broad alterations in the spatiotemporal structure of neuronal dynamics that translate into func-
26 tional deficits of diverse extent and severity (Alstott et al., 2009; Corbetta et al., 2015; Fornito et al., 2015;
27 Siegel et al., 2016). The sudden activity loss, however, triggers substantial neuroplasticity, in which activity-
28 dependent rewiring and strengthening drives functional reorganization and recovery (Murphy and Corbett,
29 2009; Zhu et al., 2010; van Meer et al., 2012), ultimately restoring partially or totally the altered brain func-
30 tions.

31 Although the biological processes involved in damage and repair are well understood (Carmichael, 2015),
32 the network mechanisms that facilitate swift response and functional recovery constitute a fundamental
33 paradigm still to be completely understood (Majdandzic et al., 2013). These mechanisms are central to
34 pinpoint the extent of affectation and evaluate the capacity of the circuit to restore function. Despite progress
35 *in vivo* through animal models (Lim et al., 2014; Cheng et al., 2014), the sheer size and intricacy of brain
36 circuits have fostered the development of *in vitro* approaches in which network damage and subsequent
37 recovery can be examined in detail (Richard et al., 2010; Siddique and Thakor, 2014; Holloway and Gavins,
38 2016). At present, however, there are no dedicated *in vitro* models that can offer a high control on the
39 delivered damage, large-scale network monitoring and detailed functional analysis of network's behavior.

40 To address these limitations, here we investigate the functional restoration of rat cortical networks *in vitro*
41 upon acute focal damage, delivered through highly focused ultrashort laser pulses that produce accurate
42 laser ablation with micrometric resolution (Vogel et al., 2005; Thayil et al., 2008). The spontaneous activity
43 of the cortical network is monitored through high-speed, whole-network calcium imaging (Orlandi et al.,

44 [2013; Teller et al., 2014, 2015](#)), which allows us to quantify in detail the network functional alterations upon
45 damage and map the network interactions along recovery. We observed that damage precipitated a sudden
46 fall of the global efficiency of the network, which gradually recovered to pre-damage levels in about 15 min.
47 Recovery was mediated by an increased spontaneous activity of the regions around the lesion core, rerouting
48 information flow to create new functional links or to strengthen existing ones. This rich plasticity evinces the
49 capacity of the neuronal circuit to respond to damage as a global system, and hints at the existence of whole-
50 network homeostatic mechanisms for circuit remodeling and functional restoration. To our knowledge, the
51 study presented here is the first *in vitro* attempt to disclose the complexity of functional restoration upon
52 acute damage, and brings new opportunities to understand resilience and recovery in brain-like circuits
53 from a network-based perspective.

54 **Materials and Methods**

55 **Ethics statement**

56 All animal procedures were performed in accordance with the authors' university animal care committee's
57 regulations.

58 **Experimental Design**

59 **Clustered neuronal cultures.** Cortical neurons were dissected from Sprague-Dawley rat embryos at 18 –
60 19 days of development, following procedures previously described ([Teller et al., 2014, 2015](#)). Briefly,
61 embryonic brains were dissected, cortical neurons dissociated by repeated pipetting, neurons suspended in
62 an appropriate culture medium, and finally plated onto 13 mm glass coverslips (Marienfield-Superior) that
63 incorporated 4 perforated circular cavities in a mold of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS). Glasses and PDMS
64 masks were attached together and autoclaved at 105°C for firm adhesion. PDMS cavities shaped *mini-*
65 *cultures* that were 3 mm in diameter, 2 mm deep and separated from one another by 1 mm. The size of the
66 *mini-cultures* was optimized to fit two of them in the field of view of the imaging system.

67 The absence of adhesive proteins in the glass substrate facilitated cell motility and aggregation, and ulti-

68 mately shaped a network of dense neuronal islands (*clusters*) connected to one another (de Santos-Sierra et al.,
69 2014; Segev et al., 2003; Teller et al., 2015). Neurons were seeded with a density of 2,500 neurons/mm²,
70 providing about 40 clusters per culture, and were incubated in plating medium [Eagle's MEM (Invitrogen)
71 supplemented with 5% fetal calf serum (FCS, Invitrogen), 5% horse serum (HS, Invitrogen), 1 μ l/ml B27
72 (Sigma), 20 μ g/ml gentamicin (Sigma), 1% 100X Glutamax (Sigma) and 0.6% glucose] at 37°C, 5% CO₂
73 and 95% humidity up to day *in vitro* (DIV) 5. The medium was then switched to changing medium [MEM
74 supplemented with 10% HS and 0.5% FUDR (5-fluorodeoxyuridine)] to limit glial cell division. From DIV
75 8 onwards cultures were maintained in final medium [MEM supplemented with 10% HS] with a periodic
76 fluid replacement every 3 days. The neuronal cultures contained both excitatory and inhibitory connections,
77 which were left active in all measurements to maximize spontaneous activity.

78 A total of $n = 14$ cultures were used in this study. They were selected from all the pool of available cultures
79 to comply two main conditions, namely a high spontaneous activity and a similar number of clusters. All
80 experiments were carried out at 20 °C.

81 **Imaging setup.** Mini-cultures were imaged in pairs at DIV 9 – 13, a developmental stage in which the num-
82 ber and position of the clusters was stable and spontaneous activity high. Neuronal activity was monitored
83 through fluorescence calcium imaging using Fluo-4-AM as Ca²⁺ probe (Teller et al., 2014, 2015). Prior
84 recording, cultures were incubated for 25 min in a transparent, pH-stable medium (recording solution, RS)
85 that contained 2 μ g of Fluo-4 per ml of solution. At the end of incubation and after washing off residual
86 Fluo-4, the cultures were transferred to an observation chamber that contained 2 ml of RS. The chamber was
87 sealed with a glass coverslip to prevent evaporation and left 5 min in darkness for stabilization.

88 The observation chamber was mounted on a multimodal microscope attached to a high speed sCMOS cam-
89 era (Hamamatsu Orca Flash 4, USB3 mode) that allowed for the simultaneous imaging of 2 mini-cultures.
90 The multimodal microscope is a modified commercial confocal microscope (Nikon C1) that integrates
91 a femtosecond-pulsed laser source for two-photon fluorescence microscopy (Mathew et al., 2009). This
92 pulsed laser input was optimized for accurate multiphoton microsurgery and optical manipulation/stimulation
93 of biological samples (Santos et al., 2013).

94 **Laser micro-surgery.** Optical surgery in combination with fluorescence imaging was achieved by setting

95 the microscope in three progressive configuration modes, termed *top EPI*, *laser*, and *bottom transmission*.
96 Fluorescence imaging of spontaneous activity was recorded using the *top EPI* configuration. Here, the
97 multimodal microscope operated as an epifluorescence microscope in an upright configuration. A mercury
98 lamp (Nikon C-HGFI) guided by an optical fiber was coupled onto the EPI-illumination port. The 'green
99 fluorescence protein' (GFP) filter set for Fluo-4 Ca^{2+} imaging consisted of a dichroic mirror (FF 509 FDI)
100 with a green filter and a blue bandpass filter (HQ470/40X). Frames were acquired with a size of 534×254
101 pixels ($6.5 \times 3.5 \text{ mm}^2$ field of view), 16-bit grayscale, and acquisition speeds in the range of 83 – 100
102 frames/s (fps).

103 Neuronal clusters were targeted using the *laser configuration*. A Ti:sapphire laser (Mira Optima 900-F,
104 Coherent) producing an ultra-short (150 fs) near-infrared (NIR) pulsed beam, with an average power of
105 400 mW in the back focal plane of the objective, was delivered onto a region of $0.7 \mu\text{m}^2$. In this setting,
106 the laser light was focused using a NIR-optimized water immersion objective with 1.05 Numerical aperture
107 (25X, Olympus). A shutter was incorporated between the attenuators to control the exposure time of the
108 laser.

109 Transmission bright field images of the cultures were obtained through the *bottom transmission configura-*
110 *tion*. To minimize the time and changes in the custom setup, the standard bottom illumination from the
111 EPI configuration was used together with the TRITC epifluorescence cube. The emission filter of the GFP
112 cube of the top configuration transmitted the excitation light of the TRITC cube and produced a normal
113 transmission image of the sample.

114 **Experimental procedure.** Neuronal spontaneous activity was evaluated through calcium fluorescence
115 imaging. To select the most appropriate cultures, activity was first recorded for 5 min in the 4 mini-cultures
116 PDMS set. The pair of mini-cultures that contained a comparable number of clusters and exhibited similar
117 activity was selected, and the entire glass adjusted to fit this pair in the field of view. One of the cultures
118 was then designated as *control* and the other one as *target*, and spontaneous neuronal activity recorded in
119 the pair for 30 min.

120 The multimodal microscope was next switched to the *laser configuration* for micro-surgery on a random
121 cluster. With assistance of a second camera (DCC 1545M, Thor Labs) and a joystick, the laser beam was

122 positioned on the cluster and manually guided. Damage was applied along the surface and edges of the
123 target cluster, effectually killing all its neurons and disconnecting the cluster from the rest of the network.
124 The microscope objective had a non-negligible chromatic aberration that produced a shift between the image
125 obtained with the camera and the ablation IR laser. This shift was compensated by moving the focal position
126 along the z axis to the plane where the damage was induced. The duration of the entire ablation operation
127 was approximately 10 min.

128 Finally, the microscope was reconfigured for florescence imaging and activity in the control and target
129 culture recorded again for additional 30 min. A bright field image of the twin mini-cultures was taken at the
130 end of the experiment to obtain a detailed characterization of the neuronal clusters.

131 All procedures were always carried out on the pair of mini-cultures, one acting as control and the other
132 as target. This ensured that all experimental manipulations, such as handling of cultures or changes in the
133 optical configuration, were experienced by both cultures. This was particularly important in the context of
134 the laser ablation, in which the long time of the procedure as well as temperature variations associated to
135 laser power could alter spontaneous activity. Post-data analysis showed that the control cultures exhibited
136 stable characteristics along the experimental pipeline, and that therefore all network changes observed in the
137 ablated culture originated from the physical damage and not from the experimental manipulations.

138 **Fluorescence signal and onset times.** Fluorescence recordings were first converted into individual frames
139 using Hokawo 2.5 software (Hamamatsu). Neuronal clusters were manually selected as Regions of Interest
140 (ROIs) over the images to extract their fluorescence intensity (average grayscale level) along the recorded
141 frames. A typical experiment contained on the order of 40 ROIs with a typical size of 40×40 pixels. The
142 raw fluorescence signal of each neuron $F(t)$ was then corrected for small drifts by detrending the signal,
143 i.e. by fitting a straight line to the baseline and subtracting it from the data. The detrended signal was then
144 normalized as $\text{DFP}(\%) \equiv 100 \times (F - F_0)/F_0$, with F_0 the fluorescence level of the neuron at rest. The nor-
145 malized fluorescence signal was analyzed to determine the onset times of activation, characterized by a sharp
146 increase of the fluorescence signal of the clusters. Following previously described algorithms (Teller et al.,
147 2014, 2015), onset times were detected as the first occurrence of the crossing between the cluster's fluores-
148 cence signal and a threshold value set as two times the average fluorescence signal of the cluster.

149 **Firing sequences.** Spontaneous activity in clustered networks is characterized by the concatenated activa-
 150 tion of two or more clusters in a short time window. These activations, termed *firing sequences* (Teller et al.,
 151 2015), provided the basis for the computation of the effective connectivity of the networks and its modular
 152 organization. Following previous studies (Teller et al., 2014, 2015), two or more clusters belonged to the
 153 same firing sequence when their coactivation time delay was lower than 200 ms. For simplicity, we will also
 154 use the term ‘firings’ to refer to these firing sequences.

155 **Network construction**

Effective connectivity computation. The effective connectivity was computed either along the entire recording or along a sliding time–window. The degree of coupling among pairs of clusters within a firing sequence was asserted through time delays (Teller et al., 2014). In this approach, the more frequently two clusters coactivate together, the stronger their connection weight, and with the directionality of the interaction given by the temporal order of coactivation. This approach provided a connectivity matrix $\mathbf{A} = \{a_{ij}\}$ that was thus weighted and directed. A null model was used to evaluate the significance of the inferred effective links and to normalize the connectivity matrix. The null model consisted in a random permutation of the times of the firing events of each cluster’s time series (Teller et al., 2014, 2015). This method erased the temporal correlations among firing clusters but preserved the average network activity. 500 surrogates were generated, each one procuring a connectivity matrix $\mathbf{A}^S = \{a_{ij}^S\}$. Significant links $\mathbf{Z} = \{z_{ij}\}$ were then set according to the z–score

$$z_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij} - \langle a_{ij}^S \rangle}{\sigma_{ij}^S}, \quad (1)$$

156 where $\langle a_{ij}^S \rangle$ is the average surrogates’ weight between clusters i and j , and σ_{ij}^S the corresponding standard
 157 deviation. High values of z_{ij} reflected strong cluster–to–cluster interactions. Negative z_{ij} values indicated
 158 links that were less connected than in a random configuration, which were disregarded and set to 0. The
 159 z–score implementation of Eq. (1) quantified the difference, in standard deviation (SD) units, between the
 160 cluster’s raw connectivity value and the surrogates’ average value. The z–score defined a fixed reference
 161 to compare different cultures and experimental conditions, and did not require the selection of an arbitrary
 162 threshold for significance.

The final set of effective links' weights $\mathbf{W} = \{w_{ij}\}$, from which all network measures were computed, was set as

$$w_{ij} = \frac{z_{ij}}{\max(z_{ij})}, \quad (2)$$

163 thus procuring a normalized effective connectivity matrix with values in the range $[0, 1]$. This normalization
164 facilitated the comparison and averaging among experiments. We verified that the procured effective con-
165 nectivity matrix \mathbf{W} using our time-delays approach was similar, in number of effective links and network
166 measures, to the one obtained using other approaches such as transfer entropy (Stetter et al., 2012).

167 **Network dynamic evolution.** Effective connectivity matrices at different time points were constructed to
168 monitor the time-varying behavior of the clustered cultures before and after damage. A sliding window
169 approach (Jones et al., 2012; Kiviniemi et al., 2011; Allen et al., 2014; Sakoglu et al., 2010) was used to
170 compute the effective connectivity matrices. Time window of length Δt (centered at time τ) progressively
171 scanned the recording without overlap. The set of firing sequences within each window was then analyzed
172 to infer the effective connectivity matrices \mathbf{W}^τ . The mean firing rate of the cultures before and after damage
173 was typically 4 and 3 firings/min, respectively. Since a minimum number of 5 firing sequences was required
174 for a reliable inference of \mathbf{W}^τ , the window size was set in the range $2.5 < \Delta t < 4$ min in both cases. An
175 inspection of all the experiments showed that this setting provided about 5–12 firing sequences per window.
176 The number of windows was therefore given by $T/\Delta t$, where $T = 30$ min is the duration of the recording,
177 leading to 9 – 12 windows for the analysis of the 'before' and 'after' damage conditions.

178 **Network measures**

179 They were computed on the time-windowed effective connectivity matrices using the Brain Connectivity
180 Toolbox (Matlab) (Rubinov and Sporns, 2010). From here on, N indicates the total number of nodes in the
181 network. The ablated node was always excluded in the analysis, both before and after damage, to prevent a
182 bias associated to network size.

183 **Nodal strength and total network strength.** The nodal strength s_i was defined as the sum of all input
184 and output weights to node i , $s_i = \sum_j w_{ij}$. The average nodal strength \bar{s} was the mean of all nodal
185 strengths, $\bar{s} = (1/N) \sum_i s_i$. The total network strength S^{net} accounted for the sum of all nodal strengths or,

186 equivalently, the sum of all weights, $S^{\text{net}} = \sum_i s_i = \sum_{ij} w_{ij}$.

187 **Density of links D .** It was defined as the fraction of total existing weighted links to all possible $N(N - 1)$
188 connections in the directed network. For a network with a total strength S^{net} , the density of links was then
189 $D = S^{\text{net}}/(N(N - 1)) = \sum_{ij} w_{ij}/(N(N - 1))$.

Global efficiency G . The efficiency E of a network of N nodes was calculated as (Rubinov and Sporns, 2010)

$$E = \frac{1}{N(N - 1)} \sum_{N=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{d(i, j)}, \quad (3)$$

190 where $d(i, j)$ denotes the minimum topological distance connecting nodes i and j . The *global efficiency* G
191 is the relative value $G = E/E_c$, where E_c refers to the efficiency of a clique formed by the same number
192 of nodes. G provided a quantification of the communication among neuronal clusters and the integration
193 capacity of the network.

194 **Time evolution of D and G .** Control and ablated cultures were measured simultaneously in each recording,
195 and analyzed identically. The time evolution of either D or G along the recording was introduced to quantify
196 the impact of laser ablation and the recovery of the culture. Thus, D and G were analyzed along different
197 time windows centered at τ , as described above. Each condition ('before damage' or 'after damage') pro-
198 cured about 10 – 15 data points. Since the window centers τ varied across experiments, the curves $D(\tau)$
199 and $G(\tau)$ were interpolated in 1 min time steps. Data was then averaged among the $n = 14$ experiments to
200 provide the final $D(t)$ and $G(t)$ curves, with $t = \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$ min.

Integrability loss Λ . It provided the relative loss in global efficiency for the ablated culture following damage. It was computed for each culture as

$$\Lambda(\%) = 100 \times \frac{\tilde{G}^{\text{bef}} - G_0^{\text{aft}}}{\tilde{G}^{\text{bef}}}, \quad (4)$$

201 where \tilde{G}^{bef} is the time-averaged global efficiency of the culture before damage (with standard deviation
202 $\text{SD}_{\tilde{G}^{\text{bef}}}$), and G_0^{aft} is the first measured value of the global efficiency just after damage.

203

204 **Integrability recovery rate Θ and recovery time T_R .** Θ characterizes the typical increase of the rela-
 205 tive global efficiency along time during recovery. It was computed for each ablated culture as $\Theta(\%) =$
 206 $\Lambda(\%)/T_R$, where T_R is the time required for the culture to attain the global efficiency before damage.
 207 T_R was determined as the moment in which the global efficiency along recovery $G^{\text{aft}}(t)$ first reached
 208 $\tilde{G}^{\text{bef}} - \text{SD}_G^{\text{bef}}$.

209 **Neighborhoods of clusters around damage.** Six neighborhoods of progressively distant rings from damage
 210 were defined. The clusters belonging to the first neighborhood were those located at a distance below a radius
 211 $r_C \simeq 0.68$ mm from the ablated cluster. This radius was set as the average inter-cluster separation and was
 212 the same for all cultures. The second and further neighborhoods were formed by those clusters located at a
 213 distance r_C from the previous ring and away from damage.

Interaction probability P . It accounted for the probability to observe intra- and inter-neighborhood ef-
 fective links. Conceptually, P rendered the capacity of a pair of neighborhood rings R_u and R_v to project
 effective connections to one another. P was computed as

$$P(R_u, R_v) = \sum_{i,j \in R_u \cup R_v} w_{ij}/M, \quad (5)$$

214 where i and j are the indexes of the clusters encompassing rings R_u and R_v , w_{ij} their weight, and M all the
 215 possible directed links that can be formed between and within R_u and R_v .

Flow of links F and ‘percent variation of flow of links’ F^* . The ‘flow of links’ F quantified the fraction
 of weighted links that flowed between two neighborhood rings R_u and R_v . F was computed in two steps.
 In a first one, the percentage $C(R_u, R_v)$ of links between rings R_u and R_v with respect to all links in which
 ring R_u participates was calculated as

$$C(R_u, R_v) = \frac{\text{links between rings } R_u, R_v}{\text{all links connecting } R_u \text{ with any other ring}} = \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in (R_u \cup R_v)} w_{ij}}{\sum_{v \neq u} \sum_{(i,j) \in (R_u \cup R_v)} w_{ij}}. \quad (6)$$

In a second step, F was determined as $F(R_u, R_v) = C(R_u, R_v)/P(R_u, R_v)$, where P is the interaction
 probability. This operation established F as a normalized measure that facilitated the averaging among
 different networks. The values procured by F for each ring pair were used to show the behavior of the

network before damage, and were denoted F_{bef} . The behavior of the network just after damage and in subsequent temporal windows τ along recovery was portrayed through the ‘percent variation of flow of links’ F^* , given by

$$F^*(\tau) = 100 \times \frac{F(\tau) - F_{\text{bef}}}{F(\tau) + F_{\text{bef}}}, \quad (7)$$

216 where $F(\tau)$ and F_{bef} are, respectively, the flow of links at a given temporal window τ and before damage. We
217 considered only the values of $F^* > 0$ to emphasize the flow of new effective links. This helped highlighting
218 those rings that increased the number of effective links with respect to the pre–damage condition.

219 **Statistical Analysis**

220 Statistical and graphical analyses were carried out with Origin 9.1 and Prism 8 software packages. One–way
221 analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze: (i) the differences between global efficiency and density
222 of links before and after damage, (ii) the difference in activity levels between neuronal neighborhoods along
223 recovery. Statistical significance was designated at $p = 0.05$ for all analyses. When appropriate, data was
224 represented and examined via box plots.

225 **Results**

226 **0.1 Focal damage on neuronal cultures**

227 We investigated the response of neuronal cultures to the destruction of a node in the network through laser
228 ablation. Cultures were an ensemble of interconnected neuronal aggregates termed ‘clusters’ grown on 3
229 mm diameter PDMS cavities. As shown in Fig. 1A, a typical culture contained about 40 quasi–spherical
230 clusters with diameters in the range 50 – 200 μm , which connected to one another through bundles of axons
231 that appeared as straight filaments. We monitored spontaneous activity in these cultures using fluorescence
232 calcium imaging, a technique that revealed neuronal activations as a sharp increase in the fluorescence signal
233 followed by a slow decay to basal levels (Figs. 1A, E, F).

234 To monitor the response of a culture to damage we used a multimodal microscope that integrated two
235 operational modes, a first one dedicated to calcium imaging and a second one dedicated to precision laser

236 surgery. Fig. 1B outlines the microscope operational modes and the experimental procedure. The key
237 advantage of the multimodal microscope is that activity monitoring and physical damage were integrated in
238 the same system, minimizing time delays between operations and ensuring that changes in neuronal network
239 behavior were solely ascribed to physical damage and not to other manipulations.

240 In a typical experiment, spontaneous activity was first monitored for 30 min in a pair of cultures (Fig. 1C),
241 which were previously selected according to their similarity in number of clusters and activity. Next, one
242 of the cultures was left unaltered as control, while the other was damaged by ablating a preset cluster from
243 the rest of the network (Fig. 1C, arrowhead). Ablation was achieved through a high-power pulsed laser
244 that scanned the entire volume of the cluster with μm resolution, locally increasing the temperature and
245 generating vapor bubbles (Fig. 1D). Both effects led to neuronal death inside the target cluster. At the end
246 of the process the ablated cluster appeared markedly bright and had no activity, signatures of full damage
247 (Figs. 1A, C). The subsequent evolution of the pair of cultures was then monitored for an additional 30 min.

248 The changes in spontaneous activity before and after damage are shown in Figs. 1E-F, which depict the
249 fluorescence traces for the boxed clusters of Fig. 1A. Before damage (Fig. 1E), all clusters exhibited a
250 strong coordinated activity, firing periodically together in the same time window. These episodes of high
251 inter-cluster coordination reflected the strong coupling of the network. After damage (Fig. 1F), the trace
252 of the ablated cluster contained just noise. Remarkably, the nearest neighbors to the ablated cluster were
253 silent for the first 10 min to gradually restore activity afterwards. The abrupt silencing of the clusters at
254 the vicinity of the ablated one evinces the strong impact of focal damage on the immediate neighborhood,
255 a feature that was observed in all experimental realizations. Although distant clusters decreased activity in
256 the experiment shown here, such a long-distance affectation was rare.

257 **0.2 Evolution of effective connectivity after damage**

258 To evaluate the alterations caused by damage, we considered a representative culture and computed the
259 effective connectivity of the network along different time windows. According to the choice for effective
260 connectivity inference, the more frequently two clusters coactivate together, the stronger the connection
261 weight. Thus, before damage (Fig. 2A), the high level of coordination among firing clusters procured a

262 strongly coupled effective network, in which the clusters with the highest strength (total incoming and
263 outgoing weighted effective connections) were uniformly spread.

264 The ablation of the target cluster (Fig. 2A, arrowhead) precipitated different events at both spatial and tem-
265 poral scales. Firstly, as shown in the raster plot of Fig. 2B, not only the targeted cluster became silent (yellow
266 band), but also its immediate neighbors (blue arrows, white bands). Secondly, some of these affected clusters
267 recovered activity to levels previous to damage in about 10 – 15 min, a feature that suggests the activation of
268 fast recovery mechanisms. And thirdly, the effective networks markedly changed in organization following
269 damage. Indeed, just after ablation the links with the highest strength appeared far from the damaged region
270 to progressively concentrate around it. Since the strength of a node reflects its degree of interaction with
271 neighbors, the recovery of the network is associated to an increase in inter-cluster activity around damage.

272 The behavior of the network as a whole was quantified through the global efficiency G (Rubinov and Sporns,
273 2010), which measures the degree of integrability in the network, i.e. its capacity for broad communication
274 and information exchange. Before damage (Fig. 2A), the average global efficiency of the network was
275 $\tilde{G}^{\text{bef}} \simeq 0.15$, which dropped to $G \simeq 0.08$ just after damage (Fig. 2B). These values provided an integrability
276 loss of $\simeq 47\%$. The global efficiency gradually increased afterwards and the network (excluding the ablated
277 cluster) attained full recovery about 15 min after damage.

278 **0.3 Evolution of global efficiency and density of links**

279 To prove that functional recovery was a general feature, we investigated a total of 14 cultures of identical
280 size, containing an average number of 40 ± 5 clusters and a similar spontaneous activity of 4 ± 1 firings/min.
281 In all cases only one node was ablated. We used the global efficiency G and the density of effective links
282 D , averaged over experimental realizations, as main descriptors for network behavior. The global efficiency
283 reflects whole network integrability, as seen before. The density of links, defined as the fraction of existing
284 weighted links with respect to all possible links, portrays the degree of dynamic interactions among clusters.
285 Figure 3A shows the average evolution of the global efficiency and density of links for the 14 ablated cultures
286 and their controls. For clarity, the presented data corresponds to the 10 min before damage and to the 15
287 min just after damage.

288 The global efficiency G (top panel of Fig. 3A) exhibited a stable behavior within experimental variability,
289 and both control and ablated cultures procured similar values of G . After damage, controls maintained
290 an overall stable behavior, although fluctuations were higher probably due to the changes in the optical
291 setup along the laser ablation procedure, which slightly increased the temperature of the recording chamber.
292 Ablated cultures, however, experienced a substantial drop in G at damage, by 50%, but gradually recovered
293 afterwards and attained values of G very similar to pre-damage levels in about 10 min. Concurrently, the
294 density of effective links D (bottom panel of Fig. 3A) also showed a stable behavior for control and ablated
295 cultures before damage, procuring similar values of D despite fluctuations. D dropped upon damage due to
296 the loss of activity around the ablated cluster, to gradually increase afterwards as activity returned.

297 Both G and D exhibited strong variability upon recovery (high standard deviations in Fig. 3A), with D even
298 exceeding the average value before damage. We ascribe the high variability to the characteristic connectivity
299 blueprint of each culture, which led to different interactions among clusters and therefore broad values of G
300 or D at a given time point. On the other hand, we view the high average value of D as a signature of the
301 recovery process itself, in which plasticity mechanisms that compensate for the loss of activity are activated,
302 increasing the number and strength of effective links among clusters.

303 The density of links D exhibited interesting traits at a network level. The circular panels accompanying
304 Fig. 3A depict effective networks at three representative time windows of the experiment shown in Fig. 2.
305 The networks spotlight the location of the 5% strongest effective links, thus portraying the most frequent
306 cluster's coactivations. Before damage, the strongest links were well spread across the network and involved
307 nearby clusters. Immediately after damage, the strongest links appeared far from the ablation core and
308 involved distant clusters. As recovery took action, the strongest links predominated around the ablated
309 cluster and as short-range interactions. These changing dynamic scenarios illustrate the complexity of the
310 recovery process and that encompasses the creation of new connectivity pathways or the strengthening of
311 existing ones.

312 To show in more detail the changes in G and D in the 14 cultures before and after damage, Fig. 3B compares
313 in the form of box plots the behavior of the cultures at different stages. Data includes the controls before
314 and after damage as well as the ablated cultures before damage, the window of 5 min just after damage

315 ('aft₀') and the window of 15 min before the end of recording and that encompasses full recovery ('aft_R').
316 A statistical comparison of the box plots indicated that the distributions of G and D values upon ablation
317 are significantly lower ($p < 0.001$, one-way ANOVA) than any other experimental condition. Thus, the
318 alterations that the cultures experienced upon ablation and subsequent recovery are associated to intrinsic
319 network changes, and not to experimental details such as the number of clusters, their spatial distribution,
320 or the culture age *in vitro*.

321 As an additional analysis, we quantified the degree of damage and recovery for each individual culture,
322 and introduced three measures, namely the integrability loss Λ , the recovery time R_T and the recovery
323 rate Θ . These measures were extracted from the evolution of the global efficiency $G(t)$ for each ablated
324 culture, as illustrated in Fig. 3C for one particular culture. The distributions of these measures for the 14
325 explored cultures (Fig. 3D) displayed a broad range of values. On average, the measures indicated that
326 global efficiency decayed by about 80% upon damage, and that recovery was attained in about 12 min at a
327 rate of 6% increase in global efficiency per minute. We also observed that there was no correlation between
328 any of these measures and experiment-specific characteristics such as the day *in vitro* of the culture or the
329 location of the ablated clusters.

330 **0.4 Activity in the neighborhood of damage**

331 The results shown in Fig. 3A evinced the pivotal role of clusters' activity during recovery, which translated
332 into the emergence of strong effective links at the vicinity of damage. To better understand this role, we
333 investigated clusters' activity in progressively distant neighborhoods with respect to the damaged region. As
334 illustrated in Fig. 4A, the clusters that shaped the ring of 'first neighbors' were those centered at a distance
335 below a characteristic radius $r_C \simeq 0.68$ mm from the ablated cluster. The second and further neighborhood
336 rings were formed by those clusters located at a distance r_C from the previous ring and away from damage.
337 For each neighborhood we plotted the average clusters' activity at different time steps, and encompassing
338 all 14 experimental realizations. As shown in Fig. 4B, we inspected activity before damage, just after dam-
339 age, and along different recovery stages. The analysis of the data procured two major results. On the one
340 hand, damage had a strong impact on activity in all neighborhoods, as indicated by the significantly different

341 distributions of clusters' activity values before and after damage ($p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA). Activity
342 dropped by 74%, 49%, and 41% for the first, second, and third neighborhoods, respectively. The remaining
343 neighborhoods reduced activity by 30%. On the other, once recovery took action, activity in the neighbor-
344 hoods gradually increased along time, although at different rates. The first and second neighborhoods, for
345 instance, boosted activity by 100% (from 0.6 to 1.2 firings/min) and 30% (from 1.0 to 1.3 firings/min), re-
346 spectively, 9 min after damage. The other neighborhoods also increased activity on average, but by a milder
347 10 – 20%.

348 Activity data also showed experiment-specific traits that are worth pinpointing. Specifically, we identi-
349 fied two experiments in which activity in the first and second neighborhoods increased after damage (black
350 arrows in Fig. 4B), and that suggests a sudden rerouting of activity flow across the network. This result
351 illustrates the complexity of physical damage in neuronal circuits and the intricate structure-function rela-
352 tionship, in which local direct loss of neurons or synaptic connections does not necessarily trigger a cascade
353 of failure at the vicinity of damage.

354 **0.5 Interaction among neighborhoods during recovery**

355 To complete the picture and gain further insight on the recovery process, we studied the degree of interaction
356 within and between neighborhoods. This interaction was quantified through the probability P of observing
357 new effective connections among clusters that belong to the same or different neighborhoods. Data was
358 computed for each culture and then averaged over cultures. As shown in Fig. 5A, clusters' interactions
359 before damage were strong and localized. Each ring of clusters exhibited a dense internal effective connec-
360 tivity and was strongly coupled with its immediate neighbors. Damage caused an overall fall of clusters'
361 interactions that affected most prominently the first and second rings around the ablated cluster. The third
362 and fourth rings maintained a high degree of internal and external interactions, which gradually extended
363 towards the rest of the network as recovery took place. These results suggest that the intermediate regions
364 of the network, i.e. those that are neither too close nor too far from damage, initiated the recovery pro-
365 cess. Remarkably, once recovery was attained, the interaction within and between neighborhoods was very
366 similar to the one before damage. Only the first ring deviated from this trend. We argue that this ring was
367 substantially sensitive to the physical wiring and activity drive of the ablated cluster, therefore substantially

368 hampering ring's recovery.

369 Given the importance of inter-neighborhood communication during recovery, we analyzed in more detail the
370 flow of effective links between neighborhoods. Fig. 5B portrays the directionality and degree of formation
371 of effective links among neighborhoods. Before damage, the 'flow of links' F_{bef} shows that all six rings
372 interacted among themselves with a similar degree, a result that is in agreement with the high coordinated
373 activity of the clusters in the network. The action of damage, emphasized here by plotting the 'variation of
374 flow of links' F^* with respect to the pre-damage condition, broke the uniformity of communication between
375 neighborhoods and made ring 3 the leader in the formation of new effective links. Indeed, as the panels
376 of Fig. 5B show, the beginning of recovery was characterized by a substantial flow of new links that either
377 diverged from ring 3 or converged towards it, and essentially involving rings 4 to 6. This behavior reinforces
378 the message that areas neither too close nor too far from damage (as ring 3 in our case) play a substantial
379 role in maintaining network activity and leading recovery. In our experiments, as recovery progressed, rings
380 1 and 2 gradually participated more actively, shaping new effective links towards the rest of the network
381 and balancing the entire system again. At full recovery, the interaction between neighborhoods procured an
382 almost uniform formation of new links.

383 Discussion

384 The *in vitro* model presented here takes advantage of the accessibility and ease of manipulation of clustered
385 neuronal cultures to investigate network's recovery and functional reorganization after acute focal damage.
386 Our results show that the neuronal clusters adjacent to the lesion core —first and second neighborhood
387 rings— were the most affected by damage, possibly due to the loss of direct physical connections. However,
388 damage did not precipitate a cascade of failure. Clusters weakly linked to the lesion core —third and fourth
389 rings— coped with damage and led recovery by establishing new functional connections or strengthening
390 existing ones. Dynamic interactions extended next to the whole network to restore its communication to
391 pre-damage levels.

392 In the experiments, the ablated cluster was chosen arbitrarily, and with the only condition that its level of
393 activity was similar to the average of the network. For the 14 cultures studied, in 60% of the experiments

394 the ablated cluster was located at the edge of the culture, and for the remaining 40% it was located at the
395 center. We could not pinpoint any significant correlation between the location of the ablated cluster and the
396 characteristics of recovery, indicating that the distance of the clusters to the damage core was the main factor
397 shaping the initial functional loss and subsequent restoration. On average, the damage locus comprised a
398 circular area 100 μm in diameter that accounted for about 3% of all neurons in the network, which were
399 irreversibly lost. The directly affected regions were those located about 0.7 mm from damage. Recovery
400 was initiated in regions about 1.5 mm away, and functional restoration reached the affected regions in about
401 15 min.

402 Reorganization of brain circuits after damage involves structural and functional changes that compen-
403 sate for both the lesion itself and remote effects in the brain (van Meer et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2013;
404 Grefkes and Fink, 2014; Siegel et al., 2016). In our experiments, however, it is unlikely that structural re-
405 modeling of inter-cluster connectivity is the major mechanism underlying the observed network recovery
406 given the short time-scales involved. Although axonal growth and formation of new synaptic connec-
407 tions are fast processes (Malyshevskaya et al., 2013; Marrs et al., 2001), few hours would be required in
408 our preparations to bypass the lost neuronal cluster and rewire the neighboring clusters among themselves,
409 which are typically 1 mm apart. This time-scale of hours is far beyond the 15 min observed for recovery.
410 Thus, we hypothesize that the central role of the physical network after damage is to support the rerouting of
411 inter-cluster dynamic interactions, reshaping information flow and functional reorganization. Upon recov-
412 ery, the major traits of the functional network, namely global efficiency and density of effective links, were
413 similar to the pre-damage condition. This suggests that the neuronal network not only restored function, but
414 that regulated itself to secure adequate operation levels. Such homeostatic mechanisms have been reported
415 in studies of brains affected by lesions (Butz-Ostendorf and van Ooyen, 2017), and have been hypothesized
416 to play a central role at early stages of recovery.

417 Despite the differences between *in vitro* and *in vivo* systems, our results are in striking accordance with
418 previous studies in mouse brains. Lim and collaborators (Lim et al., 2014) followed network activity with
419 a voltage sensitive dye upon optogenetic stimulation of different areas after cortical damage by stroke.
420 They showed that the extent of network affection depended on the connectivity strength between the mon-
421 itored brain areas and damage locus. Nearby, peri-infarct areas were severely affected, whereas more

422 distant, weakly connected areas remained unaltered. Lim's study also showed that recovery initiated in
423 distant areas and progressed heterogeneously towards the infarcted region. Despite the different size and
424 time scales of Lim's work as compared to ours, the similarity between the studies illustrates the impor-
425 tance of connectivity-based approaches to investigate recovery after local acute damage (Zhu et al., 2010;
426 Grefkes and Fink, 2014). *In vitro* experiments in combination with network analyses thus provide an ex-
427 cellent platform to relate connectivity failure with functional alterations and recovery mechanisms. The
428 gap between *in vivo* and *in vitro* architectures can be reduced through neuroengineering, which allows
429 to mimic major organizational (Aebersold et al., 2016) and dynamical (Yamamoto et al., 2018) features
430 of brain circuits while maintaining full access to neurons and connections. The analysis of damage and
431 recovery in these advanced designs will open new avenues for understanding the link between complex
432 network topologies, damage and functional resilience, more prominently in the context of modular organi-
433 zation (Sporns and Betzel, 2016) and node centrality (Alstott et al., 2009; Fornito et al., 2015).

434 The mechanisms of recovery observed in our study have important clinical implications. Cheng and cowork-
435 ers (Cheng et al., 2014) demonstrated that optogenetic stimulation of cortical areas located in the vicinity of
436 a stroke-injured mouse brain promoted overall activity and enhanced multiple plasticity-associated mech-
437 anisms, which altogether fostered whole-brain functional restoration. Translated to our *in vitro* model,
438 such stimulation protocol would correspond to induce activity in the first and second neighborhood rings
439 around the ablated cluster, which would possibly accelerate functional recovery. Our *in vitro* system is
440 highly tunable and stimulation protocols of different nature —optogenetic, electrical or chemical— can be
441 easily integrated. In combination with our present capacity of precise surgery and whole-network monitor-
442 ing, stimulation approaches could facilitate a deeper comprehension of the processes underlying network
443 reorganization during recovery, and could foster the development of new therapeutic strategies in affected
444 brains.

445 To conclude, we emphasize that the restitution of damaged circuitry and overall functional remodeling
446 constitute central mechanisms to prevent a fatal cascade of failures or the complete inoperability of neuronal
447 networks. Our work shows that functional remodeling is fast and robust. Following the recent study of
448 Harush *et al.* (Harush and Barzel, 2017), we advocate that dynamic reorganization and the access to diverse
449 pathways for information flow are much more important for resilience than previously thought. Our *in vitro*

450 approach brings new experimental opportunities and opens new frontiers to comprehend the intricacy of
451 dynamic interactions and functional reorganization in complex networks.

Figure 1: Clustered neuronal cultures and experimental procedure. **A**, Top, bright field image of a clustered neuronal culture 3 mm in diameter. Dark circular objects are neuronal clusters, and straight filaments are connections. The ablated cluster is boxed in red. Bottom, corresponding fluorescence image after damage. Healthy clusters appear gray. The ablated cluster, with all its neurons dead, appears bright. Boxed clusters are those whose spontaneous activity is represented in panels E–F. **B**, Sketch of the multimodal optical system for fluorescence imaging and laser microsurgery. **C**, Actual field of view in the experiments. Two cultures are simultaneously monitored, with one set as control and the other one as target. The latter is the same culture as in panel A, and the red arrowhead signals the ablated cluster. **D**, Laser microsurgery. The four snapshots illustrate the action of the laser as it progressively scans the cluster to be ablated, delivering in each step a high energy, high penetration pulse that kills the neurons and vaporizes water. The time interval between panels is 20 s. **E**, Spontaneous activity before damage for the 5 clusters highlighted in A. Activity is rich and all clusters fire together in a highly coordinated manner. The red arrowhead marks the cluster to be ablated. **F**, Corresponding activity after damage, with the ablated cluster completely silent. Its immediate neighbors are initially silent but recover activity after about 10 min, although with lower firing rates and amplitudes (black arrowheads). Clusters more distant from damage maintain their activity after ablation, although with a reduced firing rate.

Figure 2: Network evolution during recovery. **A**, Network effective connectivity and raster plot of activity before damage. The effective connectivity is computed on the full, 30 min duration of the recording. Nodes and links are color-coded according to their strength and weight, respectively. The darker the color, the higher the value. The yellow arrowhead marks the targeted cluster. \tilde{G}^{bef} provides the global efficiency before damage. The bottom raster plot shows the 10 min before damage, with the yellow band highlighting the cluster to be ablated. Black dots are activations. **B**, Effective connectivity evolution and raster plot after damage. The effective connectivity networks were computed in approximately 6 min time-windows. The ablated cluster is marked in black. Clusters in blue are those that became silent just after damage but recovered afterwards, with the numbers indicating their location in the bottom raster plot. G provides the global efficiency, and its relative change with respect to \tilde{G}^{bef} is shown in brackets. In the raster plot, the ablated cluster is shown with a yellow band; the initially silent clusters are shown with a white band. One of these clusters never recovered and the band encompasses the full duration of the raster plot. Grey dots are activations in clusters that did not substantially change activity after damage. Black dots are activations in affected clusters.

Figure 3: Variation of the global efficiency and the density of links upon damage. **A**, Top plot, time-evolution of the global efficiency G for control (green) and ablated (black) cultures, before and after damage. Bottom plot, corresponding density of links D . The yellow panels provide representative effective networks of the experiment shown in Fig. 2, are computed over approximately 5 min time windows (gray horizontal bars) and are thresholded to show the 5% links with the highest weight. The ablated cluster is marked in red. The networks illustrate the important changes in the distribution of links' weights along the recovery process. In both plots, data was averaged over 14 cultures and the shadings show standard deviation. For clarity, only the last 10 min before damage and the first 15 min after damage are shown. **B**, Box plots of the distribution of G (top) and D (bottom) values for the 14 cultures at different experimental conditions, comparing controls before and after damage with ablated cultures before damage, the first 5 min after ablation ('aft₀') and the last 15 min of the recording and that correspond to the recovered state ('aft_R'). For both G and D , significance (***: $p < 0.001$, one-way ANOVA) is only observed between the condition just after damage and the rest of conditions. **C**, Evolution of the global efficiency for a representative individual experiment to spotlight the definitions of the 'global efficiency loss' Δ , 'recovery time' R_T and 'recovery rate' Θ . G_0^{bef} and G_0^{aft} are, respectively, the global efficiencies before damage (dotted line for average, gray shading for standard deviation) and just after damage. **D**, Distributions of Δ , R_T and Θ for all 14 experimental realizations. All box plots span from the median to the first and third quartiles, and whiskers span from the 10th to 90th percentile.

Figure 4: Spontaneous activity in the neighborhood of damage. **A**, Construction of the ring of neighbors for a representative culture. The first neighborhood ring (red clusters) is constituted by all clusters whose centers fall within a distance $R_C = 0.68$ mm (yellow circle) from the ablated cluster (gray). The second and subsequent rings are built by identifying the clusters that are neighbors of the clusters in the previous ring according to the same distance R_C . **B**, Box plots showing the temporal evolution of the average activity in 6 neighborhoods and for the 14 experimental realizations. Before damage, activity is averaged over 30 min. The indicated times correspond to the center of the analysis windows τ . For damage (at $\tau = 3$ min, boxed) and subsequent recovery stages, activity is averaged in 6 min windows. Dotted black arrows highlight two experiments whose activity boosted up after damage. Average values of the distributions are shown as mean \pm standard deviation. The colored panels highlight the distributions that are significantly different according to a one-way ANOVA (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$).

Figure 5: Network communication during recovery. **A**, Interaction probability P among all pairs of neighborhoods. The brighter the color, the higher the formation of effective links between and within neighborhoods. Data was computed for each culture and then averaged over the 14 studied cultures. The left panel shows the neighbors' interaction before damage, with data averaged over 30 min. The three central panels show the action of damage and subsequent recovery, with each panel corresponding to about 6 min window intervals for analysis. The last panel shows the stationary recovery, with data averaged over a broader window of about 12 min. **B**, Corresponding representation of the 'flow of links' F_{bef} (before damage) and the 'percent variation of flow of links' F^* (rest of panels, calculated with respect to the pre-damage scenario). The blue curved arrow and the numbers indicate the distance from damage in terms of neighborhoods. Damage locus is symbolized as a red band. Before damage, purple arrows depict the communication flow between neighborhoods. After damage, the arrows depict the level of formation of new effective links between neighborhoods with respect to pre-damage. Arrows' thickness and color intensity are coded according to the values of F or F^* . Nodes' color is coded according to the relative strength (weighted sum of incoming and outgoing links) of the neighborhood.

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